

CAUSES AND CONSEQUENCES OF FAILURE OF LOOM ELECTRIC DRIVES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012571>

Kuchkarova Dilnoza Toptievna

Fergana Polytechnic Institute

dilnoza.toptievna1982@gmail.com

Abstract

In the article, using an artificial intelligence control module, as a result of minimizing energy consumption based on power and torque, it is possible to reduce the consumption index by 25% and increase the useful work coefficient by 90%. However, despite the current progress in the field of research on the issue under consideration, the analysis of published works showed that due to the lack of algorithms that determine the level of failure, insufficient research has been conducted on improving the energy efficiency of textile enterprises. In the analysis of the foreign and domestic experience in improving the operational reliability and energy efficiency of the electrical systems of the textile enterprise, the reliability levels of the technological processes with high energy consumption of the electrical systems were determined, and the goals and tasks of the dissertation were determined based on the development of the classification of failures.

Keywords.

Artificial neural network, electric drive, fault detector, mathematical model, control system, variable parameter

Reliability of electrical wiring is determined during the system design process and is implemented in the operational state. In industrial enterprises, many electrical devices work under normal conditions, have optimal load and are serviced on time by highly qualified technicians [1]. However, the fact that the electrical system is in a closed state in textile enterprises, the accumulation of dust, heating and erosion of insulation causes a lot of electrical and mechanical failures.

Many electric motors of looms are prone to failure due to operating in conditions different from normal. Usually, they are often installed in long-term operation mode, heavy load, asymmetrical network voltage and in places that do not match the scope of demand. Average service life of electric motors in various technological processes, taking into account the specific characteristics of the operation of electric drives in textile enterprises are presented in Table 1.

Three main prospective directions of energy saving in the textile enterprise are identified and their brief descriptions are given. During the analysis of directions, the most promising direction based on the development and application of intelligent management systems based on modern information and computer technologies was identified.

Extending the service life of electric motors in various technological processes of weaving looms shows that the specific factors of electrical equipment installation and working conditions significantly affect it. Therefore, it is always necessary to analyze the reliability of electrical equipment and take into account its variables [2].

Table 1

Average life of electric motors available on the loom

Technological process	Duration of work			
	Nominal mode		Download mode	
	Year	Hour	Year	Hour
Preparation of thread	2,6...2,7	23652	1,9...2,0	17520
Winding the thread	1,3...1,7	14892	0,8...1,1	9636
Fabric condition	2,1...2,2	19272	1,9...2,0	17520
Water supply	2,3...2,5	21900	1,6...2,0	17520
Ventilation	1,9...2,7	23652	1,0...1,6	14016

The main requirements for the fault detection process and the ways to improve the efficiency of the controlled electrical system by using modern systems of energy-saving direct and alternating current electrical systems with microprocessor control were determined.

Figure 1. Structure diagram of the loom

To improve the yarn winding process in the loom, a two-motor automatic control system (ABT) has been developed, which provides smooth synchronization of the starting, braking modes and the linear speed of the working bodies (Fig. 1). It is not possible to provide continuous control and detect failures in advance.

Using the experimental data of the one-cycle characteristic, the strength and time limitations of the weaving mechanisms on the yarns are determined (Fig. 2).

Based on the model, the transfer function of the break threads was obtained:

$$W_H(p) = \frac{F(p)}{\varepsilon_k(p)} = \frac{80p^2 + p}{0.08p^2 + 0.009p + 4.167 \cdot 10^{-6}}$$

where F is the tension strength of the thread; - deformation of threads when passing through the compensator; p is the differentiation operator.

Figure 2. Characterization of the reliability index of the thread winding part of the loom

Figure 2 shows the structural scheme of the transfer function, based on the sequence of expressions, it can be seen that the thread breaking indicator depends on the speed of the electric current (Figure 3).

Differential and Algebraic Equations for Loom Analysis:

$\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{J_1} (M_{13M} - M_{c1});$
$\frac{d\omega_{\Gamma B}}{dt} = A_{11}r_1 E' S' (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2) - M_{c2};$
$\frac{d\varepsilon_2}{dt} = \frac{1}{L^*} \left(\frac{\omega_{\Gamma B} r_1}{1 + \varepsilon_1} - \frac{\omega_2 r_2}{1 + \varepsilon_2} \right);$
$V_1 = \omega_1 \frac{R_1}{i_1}; \quad V_2 = \omega_2 \frac{R(t)}{i_2 i_3}; \quad \varepsilon = \frac{V_2 - V_1}{V_1};$
$\frac{d\omega_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{J_2} (M_{23M} - r_1 E' S' n' (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2));$
$\frac{d\varepsilon_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{L^*} \left(\frac{\omega_2 r_2}{1 + \varepsilon_2} - \frac{\omega_{\Gamma B} r_1}{1 + \varepsilon_1} \right);$

$$M_{13M} = \frac{2M_{kp}(1 + \varepsilon^*)}{\left(\frac{S}{S_{kp}} + \frac{S_{kp}}{S} + 2\varepsilon^*\right) i_1}; \quad \varepsilon = \frac{T_k d\varepsilon_k}{dt} + \varepsilon_k;$$

Each approach involves a specific problem algorithm to achieve the desired goals of the network. A centralized control scheme can achieve a theoretical global optimal object through a series of control actions. However, this approach requires an accurate distribution model and reliable power flow and state estimation results. Also network changes affect the results.

On the other hand, a decentralized control scheme uses real-time measurements to control one or a group of voltage controllers to achieve a specific goal. This affects the reliability of the looms. Formal models can be regressive, autoregressive, moving average through the practical statistical analysis of dependences of the input and output parameters of the object in controlled electric motors.

LITERATURE:

1. Martinez-Herrera, Ferrucho-Alvarez, Ledesma-Carrillo, Mata-Chavez, Lopez-Ramirez, Cabal-Yepey. Multiple Fault Detection in Induction Dvigatels through Homogeneity and Kurtosis Computation. *Energiyes* (2022) 3-16.
2. Brito, L.C., Susto, G., Brito, J.N., Duarte, M.A.. An Explainable Artificial Intelligencye Approach for Unsupervised Fault Detection and Diagnosis in Rotating Machinery. *ArXiv*, abs/2102.11848 (2021) 1-12.
3. Ibrahim, A., Anayi, F.J., Packianather, M.S., Alomari, O.A.. New Hybrid Invasive Wyeyed Optasinxon dvigatelization and Machine Learning Approach for Fault Detection. *Energiyes* (2022) 1-5.
4. Skowron, M., Orłowska-Kowalska, T., Wolkiyewicz, M., Kowalski, C.T. Convolutional Neural Network-Based Stator Current Data-Driven Incipiyent Stator Fault Diagnosis of Inverter-Fed Induction Dvigatel. *Energiyes* (2020) 1-14.
5. Sultonov R.A, Increasing the reliability of electrical drive through artificial neural networks "International Journal of Electronics, Communication Instrumentation Engineering Research and Development (IJECIERD) 2022, http://www.tjprc.org/view_paper.php?id=15986
6. Султонов Р.А., Тўқимачилик машиналари электр юритмаларини сунъий нейрон тармоқлар ёрдамида математик моделлаштириш, Фарғона

политехника институти илмий-техника журнали, махсус сон №14. Фарғона ш. 2022 йил, 82-87 б.

7. Султонов Р.А., Усмонов Ш.Ю., Абдуллажонов С.С.Ўзгарувчан ток моторларини интеллектуал бошқаришда ночизиқли қайта алоқа назорати, Фарғона политехника институти илмий-техника журнали, махсус сон №1. Фарғона ш. 2022 йил, 179-181 б.

8. Usmonov Sh.Yu., Sultonov R.A., Improvement of an intelligent control system with multi-coupled electric drives, Namangan muhandislik-texnologiya instituti ilmiy-texnika jurnali. Volume 7 Issue 1, 2022, 88-195 б. (05.00.00; №33)

9. Usmonov Sh.Yu., Sultonov R.A., Kuchkarova D.T., Tursunov A. Sh. Calculation of the speed control range of an intelligent asynchronous electric drive during rewinding raw silk, Namangan muhandislik-texnologiya instituti ilmiy-texnika jurnali, VOL6 -Issue (3) 2021, 152-156 б.

10. Usmonov Sh.Yu., Sultonov R.A., Kuchkarova D.T., Determination of the maximum permissible speed value during the rewinding of raw silk using an intelligent asynchronous electric drive, Namangan muhandislik-texnologiya instituti ilmiy-texnika jurnali, VOL6 -(3) 2021, 147-152 б.